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DEVELOPMENT OF HERBAL FORMULATION WITH AJWA SEED (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.) EXTRACT AND ZAM-ZAM WATER FOR ANTICANCER ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

Fruits of the date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.) Belonging to the family of Areaceae are very commonly consumed in many parts of the world and are a vital component of the diet in most of the Arabian countries. One of the miracles of Zamzam water has been collected by scientists and they have found certain peculiarities that make the water healthier, like a higher level of calcium. Hence, the present study was intended to evaluate ethanolic seed (Fruits of the date palm) extract of *Phoenix dactylifera* L for anticancer activities by Dalton's lymphoma ascites (DLA) models. Acute toxicity study and preliminary phytochemical screening were also studied to evaluate the toxicity. No toxicity profile was observed in rats after oral administration of the ethanolic date palm extract at the dose of 5g/kg body weight. The dose of 200 mg/kg administered seed extract of *Phoenix dactylifera* L increased the average life span of DLA cells bearing mice from 20 to 54 days when compared to that of DLA cells induced group mice. *Phoenix dactylifera* L having the property of percentage increase in body weight and significant increased level of total WBC (10.88 ± 0.44), neutrophils and a significant reduced levels of RBC (2.10 ± 0.24), hemoglobin, platelet count, eosinophils and lymphocytes (7.50 ± 0.57 ; 132.59 ± 1.00 ; 4.03 ± 0.06 and 33.65 ± 0.62) when compared to the control mice ($P < 0.05$). It can be concluded that the anticancer activity elucidated by *Phoenix dactylifera* L could be mainly due to the presences of high value class of compound like phenolic group as the major content in the seed extract.

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INTRODUCTION

Cancer is a disease of multicellular organisms [1]. Characterized by uncontrolled multiplication of subtly modified normal human cells [2]. Cancer is a leading cause of death all over the world and represents a major public health burden [3]. They constitute the second cause of mortality behind cardiovascular diseases in developed countries and the third after infectious and cardiovascular diseases in developing countries [4]. Cancer is fundamentally a disease of regulation of tissue growth. In order for a normal cell to transform into a cancer cell, genes which regulate cell growth and differentiation must be altered [5]. All of the drawbacks presently associated with available chemotherapeutic agents are impetus for the search for newer, more efficacious, and better tolerated drugs. Natural products, especially the plant kingdom, offer an inexhaustible reservoir for investigation. Plants have a long history of use in the treatment of cancer [6,7]. and the interest in nature as a source of potential chemotherapeutic agents continues [8]. The present day research and development tailored towards the discovery of new antiproliferative agents from natural products have been buoyed by improvement in the science and technology of anticancer drug discovery. Fruits of the date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera* L. Arecaceae) are very commonly consumed in many parts of the world and are a vital component of the diet in most of the Arabian countries. Date is one of the oldest known fruit crops and has been cultivated in North Africa and the Middle East for at least 5000 years [9]. The earliest record from Iraq (Mesopotamia) shows that date culture was probably established as early as 3000 BCE. Because of the long history of date culture and the wide distribution and exchange of date cultivars, the exact origin of the date is unknown, but it most likely originated from the ancient Mesopotamia area (southern Iraq) or western India [10]. One of the miracles of Zamzam water is its ability to satisfy both thirst and hunger. More recently, in the last few decades, samples of Zamzam water have been collected by scientists and they have found certain peculiarities that make the water healthier, like a higher level of calcium. [11].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Chemicals and reagents

All chemicals, reagents and solvents used in the study were of analytical grade.

Plant material:

The plant seeds materials were identified and authenticated by Dr. Pradeep, Botanist, Calicut University, Kozhikode. Voucher specimens were kept in our laboratory for future reference.

Preparation of the extract/ drug:

The granulated dried seeds of *Phoenix dactylifera* L (500 g) was packed in a Soxhlet apparatus and subjected to continuous hot percolation for using 450 ml of ethanol (95 % v/v) as solvent. The extract was concentrated to dryness under reduced pressure and controlled temperature and dried in a desiccator (yield 75 g, 15 % w/w). The extract was suspended in Zamzam water and used for further experiments.

Experimental animals:

Healthy young and nulliporous, non pregnant Sprague Dawleys female Rats weighing from 160-180 gm of 8 – 12 weeks old, were fed with a standard diet and water ad libitum. The animals were housed in spacious polypropylene cages bedded with rice husk. The animal room was well ventilated and maintained under standard experimental conditions (Temperature 27°C and 12 hours light/dark cycle) throughout the experimental period. Animal experiments were carried out followed as per pcsea the guidelines.

Acute toxicity:[12]

The ethanol and aqueous extract of *Phoenix dactylifera* L., was screened for acute toxicity, following the standard method (OECD/OCDE No:423). Healthy young and nulliporous, non pregnant Sprague Dawleys female Rats weighing from 160-180 gm of 8 – 12 weeks old, were used in this study. The test substances were administered in a single dose by gavages using a stomach tube. Animals were fasted prior to dosing (food was withdrawn overnight and water was withdrawn 3-4 hrs before drug administration). Following the period of fasting, the animals were weighed and the test substance was administered. After the substance was administered, food was withheld for 1-2 hrs

Animals were observed for behavioral changes, any toxicity, mortality up to 24hrs and observations were done up to 14 days after acute toxicity dose. Animals were observed individually for 48 hours after dosing at the first 30 minutes, periodically and during the first 24 hrs, with special attention given during the first 4 hrs and daily thereafter, for a total of 14 days. Additional observations were also made if the animals continue to display signs of toxicity. The results were tabulated in Table no.1& 2

IN VIVO ANTI-CANCER STUDY

CYTOTOXICITY STUDIES USING DALTON'S LYMPHOMA ASCITES (DLA) [12]

Induction of lymphoma

Induction of lymphoma DLA cells were obtained from Amala Cancer Research Institute, Kerala, India. The cells were maintained in vivo in Swiss albino mice by intraperitoneal transplantation of 1×10^6 cells/mouse. The DLA cells aspirated from the peritoneal cavity of the mice were washed with saline and given intraperitoneally to the experimental animals to develop ascitic tumors.

EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

Thirty Swiss albino mice were divided into five groups (n = 6) and given food and water ad libitum. The vehicle and extract were administered orally for 11 days. Group A served as control group; group B mice induced with DLA cells; group C mice induced with DLA and treatment with ethanolic seeds extract of *Phoenix dactylifera* L. at 200 mg/kg body weight from the next day of induction for 11 days; group D mice induced with DLA cells and treated with Methotrexate at 3.4mg/kg body weight from the next day of induction for 11 days; Group E mice orally administered with ethanolic seeds extract of *Phoenix dactylifera* L. at 200 mg/kg body weight for 11 days. Twenty-four hours from last dose and 18 hours of fasting, 6 animals of each group were sacrificed by cervical dislocation to measure antitumor activity. The blood was collected from the animals by incision in the jugular vein under slight anesthesia (diethyl ether). From the collected blood sample, the following hematological parameters such as RBC, WBC and hemoglobin content were estimated using a cell analyzer (Medonic CA 530, Boule Medical AB, Sweden). The differential counts of WBC were carried out in the blood smear. The results were tabulated in Table no. 3& 4

Statistical analysis

The results of various studies were expressed as mean \pm SEM and analyzed statistically using one way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's Test to find out the level of significance. Data were considered statistically significant at minimum level of $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Acute toxicity study of ethanolic seeds extract of *Phoenix dactylifera* L. based on OECD guidelines 423.

S. No	Number of animals	Dose in mg/kg	Report
1	3	5mg/kg	No death
2	3	50mg/kg	No death
3	3	300mg/kg	No death
4	3	2000mg/kg	No death
5	3	5000mg/kg	No death

In the acute toxicity studies, the various fixed doses as per OECD 423 guidelines were performed in female rats. The signs elicited by the rat such as respiration, sense of touch and sound and salivation were normal. The absence of writhing, tremour, convulsion, hind limb paralysis and diarrhea were also noted. The results obtained were tabulated in: 1&2

TABLE 2: Results of gross behavioral studies in rats on administration of seeds extract of *Phoenix dactylifera* L. 5000mg/kg/p.o.

Observation	Effects								
	Upto 3hrs	3 ½hrs	4 hrs	4 ½hrs	5hrs	5 ½hrs	6hrs	12hrs	24hrs
Respiration	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Writhing	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Tremor	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Convulsions	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Hind limb paralysis	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Sense of touch and sound	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Salivation	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Diarrhoea	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Mortality	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

+ Normal - No Effect

Table 3: Effect of ethanolic seeds extract of *Phoenix dactylifera* L. on survival period of control and experimental mice.

Groups	Survival in days	Life span (%)	Increase in life span (%)
Control	> 60	-	-
DLA	20.0 \pm 0.82	100	-
DLA + <i>Phoenix dactylifera</i> L	54.5 \pm 0.58	179.49	79.49
DLA +Methotrexate	55.25 \pm 0.50	184.60	84.60

Results were expressed as Mean \pm SD (n=6). aP<0.05 compared with normal group of mice. bP<0.05 compared with DLA-induced group of mice

Table 4: Effect of ethanolic seeds extract of *Phoenix dactylifera* L on hematological parameters of experimental mice.

Parameters	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E
Hb (g/dl)	12.99±0.70	7.50±0.57a	9.17±0.46b	10.17±0.99b	7.08±0.33b
RBC (1x10 ⁶ /mm ³)	5.20±0.46	2.10±0.24 a	2.90±0.16b	3.34±0.38b	5.06±0.25b
WBC (1x10 ³ /mm ³)	5.25±0.45	10.88±0.44a	8.15±0.30b	6.77±0.42b	5.23±0.51b
PLT (10 ³ /mm ³)	168.91±2.14	132.59±1.00a	156.00±1.81b	161.90±0.94b	172.90±1.06b
			WBC Differential count (%)		
Lymphocytes	67.08±1.06	33.65±0.62a	54.62±0.62b	61.95±0.92b	67.55±1.18b
Neutrophils	33.17±0.72	68.35±0.68a	44.98±0.78b	36.59±0.48b	33.52±0.56b
Eosinophils	5.76±0.09	4.03±0.06a	4.86 ± 0.07b	4.98±0.06b	5.65±0.16b

Results were expressed as Mean ± SD (n=6). aP<0.05 compared with normal group of mice. bP<0.05 compared with DLA-induced group of mice

Cancer therapy in the form of surgery or radiotherapy is effective when the disease is early detected but many cancers are still diagnosed when cells from a primary tumor have already metastasized to other parts of the body and the main form of treatment at this point is chemotherapy [13]. Chemotherapy entails delivering drugs systemically so that they can reach and kill the tumor cells, but most of these drugs cause severe side effects in patients and, therefore, need to be used at suboptimal levels [14]. Plants have served as a rich source of therapeutic agents for many centuries, being used themselves or as the basis for synthetic drugs [15], and despite the great developments in organic synthesis, 55% of recent chemotherapeutic drugs are derived from or based upon natural products [16]. The use of plants as food and in folk and traditional medicine has made these natural resources one of the main agents in the research and development of cancer chemopreventive drugs [17-19]. The interest in alternative therapies using natural products is increasing, especially those derived from plants, due to the increasingly high number of cancer cases worldwide. Tables 3 & 4 showed that the activity of ethanolic seeds extract of *Phoenix dactylifera* L increased the average life span of DLA cells bearing mice from 20 to 54 days when compared to that of DLA cells induced group mice, methotrexate (standard drug) also significantly increased the life span to 55 days at 3.4mg/kg body weight. These results supported by that the ethanolic seeds extract of *Phoenix dactylifera* L having the property of percentage increase in body weight in dose dependent manner when compared to that of DLA cells induced mice with *Phoenix dactylifera* L treatment mice. DLA cells induced mice showed (table 2) the significant increased level of total WBC (10.88±0.44), neutrophils and a significant reduced levels of RBC (2.10±0.24), hemoglobin, platelet count, eosinophils and lymphocytes (7.50±0.57; 132.59±1.00; 4.03±0.06 and 33.65±0.62) when compared to the control mice (P<0.05). The treatment of *Phoenix dactylifera* L seeds extract and also standard drug reversed these parameters towards normal, also treatment of *Phoenix dactylifera* L showed a significant decreased levels of WBC, neutrophils and increased levels of RBC and lymphocytes when compared with DLA control animals was observed in dose dependent manner.

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